

Scale up of light-driven hydrogen evolution to the liter scale using thiomolybdate-modified photocatalysts in a mass transport intensified loop photoreactor – Scaling synthetic procedures and operational conditions as key for scalability

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Abstract

The scalability of the light-driven hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) was studied with the molecular molybdenum sulfide clusters $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ (**{Mo₃}**) as a catalyst. The homogeneous $\text{Na}_2\{\text{Mo}_3\}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system in combination with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3](\text{PF}_6)_2$ as photosensitizer and the heterogeneous **{Mo₃}**-CN_x system were transferred from a modular, 2 mL-scale photoreactor to a mass-transport intensified, 3 L-scale stirred looping photoreactor (SLPR) and to evaluate HER activity for scalability. To enable the large-scale experiments, an efficient scaled synthesis protocol for **{Mo₃}**-CN_x was established. The homogeneous system showed strong intensification ($SPF \approx 1.98$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1.95$) for the 0.5 L-scale but suffered major loss in activity at the 3 L-scale ($SPF \approx 0.42$). In contrast, linear scale-up to 0.5 L was achieved for **{Mo₃}**-CN_x, which retained full performance ($SPF \approx 1.01$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1.61$). **{Mo₃}**-CN_x maintained stable performance at 3 L ($SPF \approx 0.75$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1$), demonstrating superior scalability. Reducing the catalyst suspension density by 66.6 % led to a 259 % increase in *TON* and a 2.58-fold enhancement in *TOF*.

Introduction

Steadily rising global greenhouse gas emissions, climate change and corresponding environmental deterioration represent stark reminders for the necessity for efficient strategies to lower the dependence on fossil fuels^[1,2]. In 2024, the global energy consumption has risen to 650 EJ and is projected to increase by around 50% over the next three decades. However, rising energy demands must be satisfied to deal with a growing global population, economy, and industry. Clean renewable energy sources can satisfy energetic requirements and mitigating negative environmental effects.^[3,4] The European Union has made substantial efforts to optimize and expand its renewable energy portfolio in pursuit of energy security and sustainability, achieving a total renewable energy share of 41% in 2022.^[5] As projected by the International Energy Agency, electrical power generation from renewables will exceed coal based sources in 2026^[6]. The inherent intermittency of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind necessitates suitable large-scale energy storage and flexibility strategies to ensure a secure and stable power supply^[7,8].

Hydrogen is an attractive alternative to fossil fuels due to its high energy density of $120 \text{ MJ} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ ^[9,10]. Photocatalytic hydrogen production is commonly enhanced using sacrificial alcohols such as methanol, ethanol, or isopropanol,^{[11,12][13]} which can also yield value-added products like aldehydes or acids^[14]. Photocatalytic systems are classified as homogeneous, heterogeneous, or hybrid, each with distinct advantages and limitations^{[15][16][17]}. Homogeneous systems couple molecular catalysts with photosensitizers (e.g., $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$, $[\text{Ir}(\text{bpy})(\text{ppy})_2]\text{PF}_6$) to operate under visible light and increase hydrogen production rates^{[18][19]}, but suffer from rapid degradation, poor solubility, and reliance on scarce noble metals. Heterogeneous systems (e.g., ZnS , TiO_2 , $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) offer greater stability but lower visible-light activity, which can be improved via doping, co-catalysts, or morphological optimization. Hybrid systems combine molecular photosensitizers with heterogeneous supports to enhance stability and activity, though current applications remain limited to milliliter scales.^[20] In addition, practical scalability of photocatalytic hydrogen production strongly depends on robust and scalable synthetic protocols^[21,22].

MoS-based systems are attractive and cost-efficient alternatives for HER due to their high activity and the relatively low cost of molybdenum^[23–26]. The all-inorganic $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ cluster has emerged as a highly active molecular HER site^[27]. Photocatalytic HER with MoS catalysts can be implemented in homogeneous or heterogeneous formats. Homogeneous HER using $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows high activity but suffers from performance losses in solvent mixtures with increasing water content^[28,29]. Heterogeneous systems, such as $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$, combine the $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ cluster with polymeric carbon nitride, improving stability and have been successfully implemented on the low-mL laboratory scale^[30]. MoS-based photocatalytic HER systems performance comparison of homogeneous and heterogeneous

photosystems has been discussed in literature and can therefore serve as valuable benchmark to evaluate scalability and corresponding scale-up requirements.^[27]

Since the absorbed photon flux determines the reaction rate of a photochemical process, absorbed photons must be quantified and treated as a reagent^{[31][32]}. Photoreactor scale-up must anticipate major scaling factors like the used light sources (emission spectrum and emission geometry), absorption spectra of used substrates, photon stoichiometry, photoreactor material (transmissivity) and geometry, the irradiated reaction surface, light intensity, the distance between light source and reactor and the optical pathlength. In addition, reaction temperatures, efficient heat exchange, sufficient mixing, and flow patterns must be considered.^[32-34] The large number of influencing parameters and their complex interdependencies lead to a high degree of complexity during scale-up. A scaled photoreactor must ensure thorough irradiation of the reaction solution, which depicts a particular challenge due to exponential light attenuation along the pathlength of an absorbing medium. Therefore, irradiation efficiency will be compromised if a photoreactor is scaled by size alone.^[35] The presence of light intensity gradients along the optical pathlength of a photoreactor inevitably leads to undesirable spatial variations in the local reaction kinetics.^[36] Mass-transport limitations can further constrain photochemical reaction rates, making both convective and diffusive transport critical. Even with sufficient local photon availability, efficient delivery of reactants to the irradiated zones and removal of products are required. Controlled mixing can thus serve as a process-intensification strategy in scaled photoreactors by promoting repeated exposure of catalysts and substrates to the local radiation field.^[37]

Falling film photoreactors (FFPs) enable direct geometrical scale-up using the irradiated reactor surface while maintaining constant optical path length and similar irradiance across scales^[35,38]. Their thin liquid films possess large area-to-volume ratios, reduce diffusion distances, enhance heat and mass transfer, and mitigate light attenuation, minimizing reaction-rate gradients and byproduct formation in process scale-up^[38-40]. Despite this, FFPs are unsuited for slurry-type reactions requiring efficient suspension of particulate matter^[35].

Scaling a photoreactor by size increases the optical path length, making mass-transport intensification through mixing essential. Lee et al. demonstrated scale-up of a Taylor-flow vortex reactor from gram to kilogram-per-day production, achieving a >300-fold increase in productivity with safe long-term operation^[41]. Li et al. demonstrated that a stirred loop reactor for light-driven hydrogen evolution (HER) could be scaled by more than an order of magnitude, with apparent quantum yield increased up to 17-fold through mass-transport intensification^[42]. Similarly, Gaulhofer et al. improved pilot-scale reactor performance by a factor of 2.4 using static mixers^[43]. Spinning disk reactors represent another scalable design that enhances mass transfer and process intensification^[44].

In this work, homogeneous ($\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) with $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3](\text{PF}_6)_2$ as photosensitizer and heterogeneous ($\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$) photocatalytic systems for hydrogen evolution (HER) were investigated regarding their scale-up requirements from a 2 mL vial to 0.5 L and eventually 3 L stirred loop photoreactor (SLPR) scale. A comprehensive analysis of reaction parameters, including especially radiation field parameters such as apparent quantum efficiency and external photonic efficiency was conducted to evaluate the transferability of the studied photocatalytic systems from laboratory to application.

Photoreactor Setups and Performance Metrics

Photoreactor Setups

Figure 1 Pictures of used photoreactors in scale, **a** 2 mL scale Modular Photoreactor equipped with 8 5 mL GC vials, **b** 0.5 L SLPR and **c** 3 L SLPR and corresponding irradiation modules.

In recent studies, the Modular Photoreactor (see Figure 1 **a**) has been successfully used for comprehensive studies of homogeneous MoS-based HER, enabling systematic investigation of solvent ratios, light intensity, and mixing on the laboratory mL-scale^[29]. It can be equipped with a magnetic stirrer to ensure appropriate mixing of slurry-type catalytic systems and was therefore chosen as a small-scale benchmarking platform for a comparative analysis of homogeneous and heterogeneous MoS-based HER regarding scalability and scale-up requirements. Its multi-batch configuration, comprising eight 5 mL GC vials, enables simultaneous and homogeneous sample irradiation and allows kinetic analysis via serial gas chromatographic probing of hydrogen in the headspace. For scale-up investigations, the 0.5 L SLPR concept proposed by Li et al.^[42] was extended with a cooling jacket (see Figure 1 **b**) and scaled by a factor of six to a reactor size of 3 L (see Figure 1 **c**). To counteract the local reaction rate gradients caused by light attenuation, the SLPR uses forced convection through the internal draft tube and the outer annular region of the reactor to recycle the reaction solution internally. Reactants are moved from the centre of the reactor (shadowed dark region) towards the irradiated annular region while ensuring a high suspension quality. In addition, inert gas can be purged through the reactor that is used for continuous GC sampling. The purge gas can also cause an intensification of the performance as it was found to significantly improve the hydrogen production for a Pt-CN_x photocatalyst^[42].

Hydrodynamics of the SLPR

Scaling a photoreactor solely by volume inevitably increases its optical pathlength and thus will compromise scale independent comparability, due to a disproportionally high decrease of the ratio of irradiated reaction volume and total reaction volume (V_r). By increasing $V_r = 2$ mL (5 mL GC vial, $d = 14.7$ mm) to 3 L (3 L SLPR, $d = 100$ mm), the volume rises by a factor of 1500, whereas

Figure 2: a Correlation between reactor tube diameter and A_s for the 5 mL GC vial, 21 mL Schlenk tube, 0.5 L SLPR and 3 L SLPR at respective volumes of 2 mL, 10 mL, 0.5 L and 3 L, respectively. b schematic illustration of the working principle of the SLPR looping.

the irradiated cylindrical mantle surface increases only by a factor of 46 (9.2 to 422 cm^2). Simultaneously, the optical path length increases by a factor of 6.8, while at the same time the penetration depth of the light remains constant for a given catalyst suspension loading, leading to a severe shrinkage of the fraction of the irradiated reaction zone in relation to the total reactor volume. This eventually leads to an increase of the shadowed reactor V_r . The relation between V_r and the surface available for illumination can be evaluated using the specific surface area (A_s) described by Eq. (1). Figure 3 a illustrates the significant decrease of A_s with increasing optical pathlength of a tubular photoreactor, emphasizing the need for sufficient mixing. The SLPR meets this requirement by enforcing intense convective circulation, thereby continuously transporting reactants between dark and illuminated regions effectively counteracting light attenuation induced reaction rate gradients (see Figure 2 b).

Performance Metrics

Photoreactor performance was evaluated using the following performance metrics.

- a) The specific surface area (A_s). A_s can be derived as the ratio of the irradiated area (A_{irr}) and the reactor volume V_r according to Eq. (1).

$$A_s = \frac{A_{irr}}{V_r} \quad (1)$$

- b) The mean hydrogen evolution rate $r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}}$

$$r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}} = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2}}{\Delta t} \quad (2)$$

- c) The volumetric (up-)scaling factor V_{scale} , with $V_{r,2} > V_{r,1}$

$$V_{\text{scale}} = \frac{V_{r,2}}{V_{r,1}} \quad (3)$$

- d) The scale up performance factor $SPF(t)$ with the cumulative hydrogen production $n_{\text{H}_2, \text{V}_2}(t)$ in the scaled reactor and $n_{\text{H}_2, \text{V}_1}(t)$ in the small-scale photoreactor

$$SPF(t) = \frac{n_{\text{H}_2, \text{V}_2}(t)}{n_{\text{H}_2, \text{V}_1}(t)} \cdot \frac{1}{V_{\text{scale}}} \quad (4)$$

- e) The turnover number TON

$$TON = \frac{\Delta n_{\text{H}_2}}{n_{\text{cat, active}}} \quad (5)$$

- f) The turnover frequency TOF

$$TOF = \frac{d \text{ TON}}{d t} \quad (6)$$

- g) The apparent quantum efficiency AQE using the absorbed photon flux q_{abs}

$$AQE = \frac{r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}}}{q_{\text{abs}}} \quad (7)$$

- h) The photonic efficiency preservation $AQY_{\text{pres}}(t)$ with the apparent quantum yield at a given reaction time t in the scaled photoreactor $AQY_{\text{V}_2}(t)$ and $AQY_{\text{V}_1}(t)$ in the small-scale photoreactor

$$AQY_{\text{pres}}(t) = \frac{AQY_{\text{V}_2}(t)}{AQY_{\text{V}_1}(t)} \quad (8)$$

- i) The external photonic efficiency ξ_{ext} using the external photon flux q_{ext} emitted by the light source.

$$\xi_{\text{ext}} = \frac{r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}}}{q_{\text{ext}}} \quad (9)$$

- j) And the efficiency of irradiation of the reactor (ξ_{irr})

$$\xi_{\text{irr}} = \frac{q_{\text{abs}}}{q_{\text{ext}}} \quad (10)$$

Results and Discussion

Different reactor scales (2 mL GC vial, 0.5 L and 3 L stirred looping photoreactor - SLPR) were studied using homogeneous ($\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and heterogeneous ($\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$) photocatalytic reaction systems with respect to the light driven HER performance and scale up requirements. An overview of the used catalytic conditions are listed in Table 1. A detailed HER performance comparison is provided in section 4 ESI.

Table 1: Overview of the used catalytic conditions for photocatalytic hydrogen production using $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$.

Nr.	reactor	stirring	V_r / mL	Solvent ratio (MeOH:H ₂ O)	$\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ / μmol	$\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ / μmol
1	5 mL GC vial	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
2	5 mL GC vial	500 rpm	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3	5 mL GC vial	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
4	5 mL GC vial	500 rpm	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
5	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
6	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	no	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
7	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	yes	2	9:1		$6.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
8	5 mL GC vial	600 rpm	2	1:9	$1.05 \cdot 10^{-1}$	
9	Schlenk tube ^[30]	yes	10	1:9	0.12	
10	0.5 L SLPR	740 rpm	470	9:1		0.141
11	0.5 L SLPR	740 rpm	480		25.20	
12	0.5 L SLPR ^[42]	560 rpm	460		42.11 (Pt-CN _x)	
13	3 L SLPR	no	2820	9:1		0.845
14	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2820	9:1		0.845
15	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2820	1:9		0.845
16	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	151.20	
17	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	106.25	
18	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	70.83	
19	3 L SLPR	740 rpm	2880	1:9	35.42	

Since the rate of a photochemical reaction typically scales with q_{abs} , q_{ext} was normalized to V_r , yielding the external volumetric photon flux q_{vol} to enable reactor scale independent comparability. For photocatalytic studies performed on the 2 mL scale at $q_{\text{ext}} = 1.3 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ a q_{vol} of $0.047 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ per vial was determined based on $\xi_{\text{irr}} = 7.24\%$ derived from photonic characterization (see ESI section 5) of the modular photoreactor. For catalytic experiments carried out using the 0.5 L and the 3 L SLPR, full absorption was assumed due to the favorable positioning of the LED modules relative to the SLPR (reactor mantel entirely covered by the radiation field) and thus $q_{\text{ext}} = q_{\text{abs}}$. The resulting calculations of the photonic characteristics of the used reactors and literature results^[29,30,42] are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of irradiation characteristics of different reactors of this work and other reports.

Nr.	reactor	$\lambda_{LED}/$ nm	$V_r /$ mL	$A_{irr} /$ cm ²	$A_s /$ m ² · m ⁻³	$q_{ext} /$ μmol · s ⁻¹	$q_{abs} /$ μmol · s ⁻¹	$q_{vol} /$ μmol · (s · mL) ⁻¹	$\xi_{irr} /$ %
1	5 mL GC vial	455	2	4.34	217.16	1.30	0.09	0.047	7.2
2	5 mL GC vial	455	2	4.34	217.16	1.30	0.09	0.047	7.2
3	5 mL GC vial	365	2	4.34	217.16	1.30	0.09	0.047	7.2
4	5 mL GC vial	365	2	4.34	217.16	1.30	0.09	0.047	7.2
5	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	455	2	4.34	217.16	2.15	0.11	0.056	5.2
6	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	453	2	4.34	217.16	19.00	0.80	0.399	4.2
7	5 mL GC vial ^[29]	453	2	4.34	217.16	19.00	0.80	0.399	4.2
8	5 mL GC vial	365	2	4.34	217.16	1.30	0.09	0.047	7.2
9	Schlenk tube ^[30]	420	10	12.75	127.50	2.24	-	-	-
10	0.5 L SLPR	455	480	126.0	26.25	22.11	22.11	0.047	100
11	0.5 L SLPR	365	470	126.0	26.81	22.58	14.23	0.030	100
12	0.5 L SLPR ^[42]	365	460	126.0	27.39	11.51	4.70	0.010	40.8
13	3 L SLPR	455	2820	465.0	16.49	132.67	132.67	0.047	100
14	3 L SLPR	455	2820	465.0	16.49	99.50	99.50	0.035	100
15	3 L SLPR	455	2820	465.0	16.15	64.71	64.71	0.022	100
16	3 L SLPR	365	2880	465.0	16.15	64.71	64.71	0.022	100
17	3 L SLPR	365	2880	465.0	16.15	64.71	64.71	0.022	100
18	3 L SLPR	365	2880	465.0	16.15	64.71	64.71	0.022	100
19	3 L SLPR	365	2880	465.0	16.15	64.71	64.71	0.022	100

Figure 3: Catalytic performance comparison of homogeneous light-driven HER without stirring and stirring at 600 rpm on the 2 mL reaction scale under 455 nm LED irradiation.

Homogeneous light-driven HER with $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as photocatalyst was studied on the 2 mL scale with a solvent ratio of 9:1 MeOH/ H_2O under 455 nm and 365 nm irradiation. Experiments were conducted without and with stirring at 500 rpm to enable comparability with scaled experiments using the SLPR. A significant decrease of the overall TON by approximately 23.9-26.8 % was observed for stirred experiments compared to the unstirred experiments (see Table 1, entry 1-4) independent of the used wavelengths (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). This observation aligns well with previous findings reporting a TON decrease by $\approx 28.9\%$ ^[29] upon stirring. A maximal TON of 5017 was observed after 3.75 h irradiation with a 455 nm LED without stirring, equivalent to the production of 3 μmol H_2 . In the literature, homogeneous HER using $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as photocatalyst conducted at similar conditions was reported with an overall TON of 16633 after 6 h of irradiation without stirring^[29]. The lower TON observed in this work results from the 37.4 % shorter reaction time and a 39.7 % lower q_{ext} compared to literature. In addition, a stirring independent drop of the observed reaction rate and TOF of $\approx 83\%$ and $\approx 75.6\%$ during 3.75 h of operation for 455 nm and 365 nm irradiation were found, respectively (see Table 1, entry 1-4). For irradiation with 365 nm LED, the TON generally decreased by around 68 % compared to 455 nm irradiation, independent of stirring (see Figure 4 b and d). This behavior is a result of the lower absorbance of the used $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ PS in the UV region^[45,46]. The obtained results

Figure 4: Catalytic performance comparison of homogeneous light-driven HER without stirring and stirring at 600 rpm on the 2 mL reaction scale under 365 nm LED irradiation.

indicate fast deactivation of the homogeneous reaction system, which is in line with literature reports where an 8-fold activity drop over the course of 5 h was reported. In the literature it is argued that the deactivation of the reaction systems is not only due to a PS and SA depletion but also due to a gradual degradation of $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$.^[27] The rapid breakdown of catalytic performance depicts a major hurdle for long-term operation in scaled photoreactors. Therefore, strategies to counteract deactivation processes must be elaborated to ensure scaled application.

Figure 5 depicts the results of heterogeneous light-driven HER using $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ as photocatalyst in 1:9 MeOH/ H_2O with 365 nm irradiation for 3 h and constant stirring at 500 rpm on the 2 mL scale using the same q_{vol} as for homogeneous system (see Table 1, entry 8). To ensure inter system comparability based on the amount of active catalyst, *TON* and *TOF* calculations for the heterogeneous case were based on the $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ loading of 3.7% (w/w, $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$) derived by SEM/EDX characterization (see section 3 ESI). As this technique probes only local surface regions, the values represent apparent *TON* and *TOF* and may not reflect the global catalyst loading of the entire batch. They are therefore used primarily for comparative purposes with the homogeneous reference HER system. Compared to the best performing reaction conditions of the homogeneous system (455 nm LED irradiation, no stirring, Figure 3 b), an around 1090-fold (830-fold, with stirring) decrease in *TON* and a 870-fold (663-fold, with stirring) decrease in *TOF* was observed for the

Figure 5: Catalytic performance of heterogeneous light-driven HER with stirring (600 rpm) on the 2 mL reaction scale under 365 nm LED irradiation.

heterogeneous reaction system. Interestingly, only a slight decrease of the TOF over time was observed, indicating little deactivation of the photocatalytic system, which is a major advantage for long term operation. For the heterogeneous reaction system, a TON of 4.6 can be reported, aligning well with the TON of 24.9 calculated for 10 mL scale experiments carried out over 7 h in a stirred 21 mL Schlenk tube under 420 nm LED irradiation and a $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ loading of 0.85 % (w/w)^[30]. The advantage of long term stability of the heterogeneous $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ system compared to the homogeneous system becomes even more relevant when considering the absolute amount of produced hydrogen. In comparison to the homogeneous system, about 5 times (4 times, with stirring) less hydrogen is produced, while the TON decreased by 1090 to 830 times. The same observation holds for the mean reaction rates.

In summary, the 2 mL-scale experiments revealed superior overall activity of the homogeneous reactions system that comes at the cost of fast deactivation and a drop of activity with stirring. Consequently, scalability of the homogeneous reaction system requires elaboration of strategies to counteract excessive deactivation to enable long term operation at larger scale. The use of pulsed irradiation is a potential approach, as recently reported by Kolbinger et al. An overall performance and photonic efficiency increase for a molybdenum sulfide based homogeneous photocatalyst system was realized by electronic pulsation of the used LEDs^[47,48]. Another report on the positive effect of dynamic irradiation describes a 10-fold boost of $TONs$ in homogeneous ruthenium-based light-driven water oxidation, with dynamic irradiation realized by recycling of reaction solution through a partially irradiated and shaded capillary reactor.^[49] Further, Guba et al. demonstrated intensification of photocatalytic reactions for both electronic pulsation of LEDs and hydrodynamically induced dynamic irradiation.^[50,51]

Figure 6: Catalytic performance of homogeneous light-driven HER at stirring (740 rpm) on the 0.5 L reaction scale under 455 nm LED irradiation using the SLPR.

In the first scale-up step, the total reactor volume was scaled to about 0.5 L with the SLPR, which can be filled with about 0.47 L of reaction solution. Results for the homogeneous reaction system with 455 nm LED irradiation and a stirring speed of 740 rpm are presented in Figure 6. The HER experiment was conducted over 25.8 h until the observed reaction rates approached 0, indicating complete deactivation of the photocatalytic system. Overall, a high absolute hydrogen production of 3,509 μmol ($r_{\text{H}_2, \text{mean}} = 136 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) and a TON of 24,884 ($TOF = 16.08 \text{ min}^{-1}$) were observed. After 3.75 h, hydrogen production reached around 1,400 μmol , resulting in a ≈ 465 -fold increase compared to the 2 mL scale experiments (see Figure 3 a). Since V_r was only scaled by $V_{\text{scale}} = 235$ a $SPF \approx 1.98$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1.95$ were calculated, indicating an intensification of the hydrogen evolution and an increased photon utilization in the 0.5 L SLPR compared to small-scale experiments conducted in the modular photoreactor. This observation can be explained by the significantly decreased optical pathlength of the 5 mL GC vial compared to the 0.5 L SLPR (see Figure 2 a) consequently leading to transmission of light through the 5 mL GC vial thus lowering the absorbed photon flux. SPF and AQY_{pres} can have the following implications:

$SPF(t) = 1$ linear scale-up – hydrogen production scales linearly with volume

$SPF(t) < 1$ loss of performance upon scale-up

$SPF(t) > 1$ increase of performance upon scale-up

$AQY_{\text{pres}}(t) = 1.0$ photonic performance fully preserved upon scale-up

$AQY_{\text{pres}}(t) < 1.0$ decreased photonic performance

$AQY_{\text{pres}}(t) > 1.0$ Increased photonic performance

Figure 7: Catalytic performance comparison of heterogeneous light-driven HER using {Mo₃}-CN_x and Pt-CN_x on the 0.5 L SLPR scale under 365 nm LED irradiation SLPR at stirring with respective stirring speeds of 740 rpm and 560 rpm.

This observation also aligns with the lower decrease in r_{H_2} and TOF for the 0.5 L SLPR ($\approx 53.4\%$, 3.75 h) compared to the 83.5% in the small-scale experiments. It is hypothesized that these findings result from the impact of dynamic irradiation in the SLPR on light-driven HER using MoS-based photocatalysts^[47,48]. In the SLPR fluid elements are constantly moved from the draft tube region (center of the reactor tube, less irradiated) to the intense irradiated annular region of the reactor resulting in dynamic irradiation with a frequency and duty cycle governed by the stirring speed. Dye-based analysis of the flow field revealed residence times of 1.99 s within the draft tube and 2.84 s for the annular region of the 0.5 L SLPR at 740 rpm^[42]. This fluid motion causes dynamic irradiation in the 0.5 L SLPR with a frequency of 0.207 Hz and a duty cycle of 58.75 : 41.25%. To confirm the hypothesis on the impact of dynamic irradiation, the complex interplay between hydrodynamics and corresponding radiation field modulation in the SLPR must be understood in detail.

The results of experiments with the heterogeneous HER system on the 0.5 L scale in the SLPR with 365 nm LED irradiation and a stirring speed of 740 rpm are depicted in Figure 7 a and b. HER was conducted for 21.5 h. Over the course of the entire experiment a decrease in r_{H_2} and TOF of 37.9% was observed, indicating significantly lower deactivation of {Mo₃}-CN_x compared to the homogeneous reaction system. Post catalysis SEM/EDX analysis indicated

that the catalyst largely retains its carbon nitride–domain and $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ loading after catalysis. Even though post catalysis characterization indicates partial sulfur loss, $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ maintains its MoS-modified carbon nitride architecture, supporting its durability and sustained catalytic functionality (for more details see section 3.3 ESI). An overall hydrogen production of $689.6 \mu\text{mol}$ ($r_{\text{H}_2,\text{mean}} = 32 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) and a TON of 27.4 ($TOF = 0.02 \text{ min}^{-1}$) can be reported. Compared to the homogeneous 0.5 L SLPR experiment, an overall 5-fold lower absolute hydrogen production and a 4.25-fold decrease of $r_{\text{H}_2,\text{mean}}$ was observed. Nevertheless, the increased stability of the heterogeneous reaction system allows long-term operation.

In comparison to the heterogeneous 2 mL scale experiment, absolute hydrogen production reached around $116.7 \mu\text{mol}$ after 3 h resulting in an about 240-fold increase compared to the small-scale experiments (see Figure 5 a). Since V_r was scaled by $V_{\text{scale}} = 240$ a $SPF \approx 1$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1.61$ were determined, indicating linear scalability and an increase of photonic efficiency upon scale-up.

In comparison, with the Pt- CN_x system in the 0.5 L SLPR, a 29.6 % lower absolute hydrogen production of about $700 \mu\text{mol}$ after 21.5 h was observed (see. Figure 7 c and d)^[42]. However, for experiments with $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$, a 1.67-fold lower active catalyst amount was used (see Table 1 entry 11 and 12). After a reaction time of $t = 21.5 \text{ h}$, a $TON = 27.9$ ($TOF = 0.018 \text{ min}^{-1}$) for Pt- CN_x and a $TON = 27.4$ ($TOF = 0.021 \text{ min}^{-1}$) for $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ were determined, comparable to the Pt- CN_x system. Considering the approximately three orders of magnitude lower costs of Mo compared to Pt at comparable HER activity, the $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ -based reaction system represents an economically very attractive alternative for application in light-driven photocatalytic HER^[23–26].

In a further scale up step the 0.5 L SLPR was scaled to 3 L ($V_{\text{scale}} = 6$). As a reference experiment, homogeneous HER was performed over 37.13 h without stirring (see Figure 8 a and b) while maintaining the same q_{vol} of $0.047 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ as for the 2 mL and 0.5 L scale experiments. Compared to the 2 mL scale (455 nm LED irradiation, no stirring, 3.75 h) with a corresponding $V_{\text{scale}} = 1410$, $SPF \approx 0.169$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 0.170$ were determined, indicating poor scalability and significantly decreased photonic efficiency upon scale-up

Figure 8: Catalytic performance comparison of homogeneous light-driven HER without stirring and stirring at 740 rpm on the 3 L reaction scale under 455 nm LED irradiation using the SLPR.

without stirring. Interestingly, deactivation of the homogeneous catalytic system occurred in an almost linearly instead of an exponential decay as for the 2 mL and 0.5 L scale (for comparison see Figure 3 and Figure 6). r_{H_2} and TOF decreased by $\approx 15.4\%$ after 3.75 h and further by $\approx 82.1\%$ after 37.13 h. The 3 L SLPR has a 6.8-times larger optical pathlength compared to the 5 mL GC vial used for the 2 mL scale experiments. Since V_r was scaled by a factor of 1410 but the irradiated reactor surface only by a factor of 207, large zones of the 3 L SLPR V_r were not irradiated. The observed linear deactivation behavior might result from these large dark zones, in which no HER occurs, but also PS degradation. Since no stirring is applied, PS can only move into the irradiated zones by diffusion as the rate limiting step, i.e. deactivation is mass transport limited. This behavior is in line with the observed almost linear deactivation.

Results of HER in the 3 L SLPR with stirring at 740 rpm are shown in Figure 8 c and d over 20.68 h, but with a reduced q_{vol} of $0.031 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$. Even though the photon flux was reduced to 3/4 of the original value, the produced absolute hydrogen amount ($t = 20.68$ h) increased by merely 62 % from 3,195 μmol to 8,315 μmol through stirring, emphasizing the importance of appropriate mixing in scaled application.

Compared to the 0.5 L scale ($V_{\text{scale}} = 6$), a $SPF \approx 0.417$ and $AQY_{\text{ret}}(t) \approx 0.556$ was determined, indicating significant losses in performance and photonic efficiency during the transfer. These losses cannot solely be explained by photonic limitation due to the reduced photon flux. Assuming operation within the photon limited reaction regime, an increase of the produced hydrogen productivity by 25 % can be expected if the q_{vol} is increased to $0.047 \mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$. In this case SPF would increase to 0.521, which still indicates a significant loss in performance during scale-up.

To evaluate potential losses in performance due to changing hydrodynamics within the 3 L SLPR compared to the 0.5 L SLPR, the mixing time and corresponding dynamic irradiation conditions were evaluated (detailed description see section 2 ESI). Even though the mixing time evaluation within the draft tube and annular region revealed minor changes in frequency (3 L SLPR: 0.174 Hz; 0.5 L SLPR: 0.207 Hz) and duty cycle (3 L SPLR: 50:50 %; 0.5 L SLPR: 59:41 %), these changes cannot explain the significant performance losses. Instead, major differences in light distribution along the optical path of the annular region of the 0.5 L and 3 L SLPR might be the reason for the observed performance loss. Figure 9 depicts the steep decrease of light intensity along the optical pathlength of the SLPR. The much lower light intensity within the annular region of the 3 L SLPR might cause the observed losses during scale up and might be mitigated by additional intensification of the radial mass transport within the annular region of the SLPR.

Intensifying radial mass transport to compensate (self-)shadowing of photochemical reaction systems can for instance be realized by installing static mixers, as demonstrated for annular emersion lamp reactors^[43,52,53]. Furthermore, it is known that the flowrate of the inert gas stream used for continuous hydrogen detection affects the performance of HER. Li et. al identified the purge gas flowrate as key intensification parameter in Pt-CN_x based HER within the 0.5 L SLPR^[42]. Since a constant inert gas flowrate of $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ was used for all SLPR experiments, adaptation of the gas flow rate to $V_{\text{scale}} = 6$ might be required to maintain HER performance at larger scale.

Figure 9: Light attenuation along the optical pathlength of the SLPR based on a molar absorption coefficient of $15,000 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ of $\text{Ru}[\text{bpy}_3]^{2+}$.

Figure 10: Catalytic performance of homogeneous light-driven HER at a solvent ratio of 1:9 MeOH/H₂O at stirring (740 rpm) on the 3 L reaction scale under 455 nm LED irradiation using the SLPR.

HER with the homogeneous Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] · 5 H₂O as photocatalyst is sensitive to the water content in the reaction solution. Increasing water content leads to a pronounced loss in catalytic performance [28,29]. To also consider this effect, applicability of the homogeneous photocatalytic reaction system was tested with a solvent ratio of 1:9 (MeOH/H₂O) under 455 nm LED irradiation (0.047 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) and stirring at 740 rpm, as applied in heterogeneous HER experiments. The increasing water content caused a rapid deactivation of the photocatalytic reaction system, reflected by a r_{H_2} and TOF decrease of 93.3 % after 19.4 h reaching 83.9 % already after 4 h of irradiation (see Figure 10). The strong dependence on flammable solvent mixtures depicts a major safety hazard for scaled application and represents a critical weakness of homogeneous Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃] · 5 H₂O based HER for scalability.

Since the feasibility of a light-driven photocatalytic system for scaled application strongly depends on the scalability of synthetic protocols [21,22], a comparative analysis of two different {Mo₃}-CN_x batches was performed on the 3 L scale. {Mo₃}-CN_x materials were prepared using a procedure proposed by Beranek et al. (batch 1) [30] and a scaled approach presented in this work (batch 2). SEM/EDX characterization of batch 2 indicated a [Mo₃S₁₃]²⁻ loading of 2.6 % (w/w, {Mo₃}-CN_x) (see section 3 ESI). Figure 11 depicts the results for catalytic experiments over 21.55 h and 27.85 h (batch 1 and batch 2) under 365 nm LED irradiation (0.047 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) and stirring at 740 rpm. For both evaluated batches high hydrogen productivities at a reaction time of 21.55 h of 3,046 μmol (batch 1) and 3,148 μmol (batch 2) with comparable $r_{\text{H}_2}(t)$ of 141-146 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and TOF of 0.016-0.023 min^{-1} were observed. It can be

Figure 11: Catalytic performance comparison of heterogeneous light-driven HER using $\{Mo_3\}-CN_x$ prepared using original literature procedure and scaled procedure on the 3 L SLPR scale under 365 nm LED irradiation SLPR at stirring (740 rpm).

concluded that used synthetic protocols do not influence the HER activity, outlining the potential of $\{Mo_3\}-CN_x$ for scaled application.

When comparing the HER performance of batch 2 at the 3 L scale with results from 0.5 L SLPR experiments ($V_{\text{scale}} = 6$), $SPF \approx 0.754$ and $AQY_{\text{pres}} \approx 1$ were determined, indicating that the SPF increase is not linear even though the quantum efficiency is preserved. This also aligns with the 24.2% lower q_{vol} for the 3 L SLPR experiments, and indicates that the observed hydrogen evolution is still in the photonic limited regime. It can be concluded that volume normalized scale-up considerations are not suited as for transferring this reaction. Instead the total incident photon flux is the required performance indicator, which also indicates that no additional performance limitation appeared during scale-up and a linear increase of the HER performance for the heterogeneous reaction system was observed.

Due to the high degree of absorption of ≈ 1 at a suspension density of $1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$, additional experiments on the effect of suspension density were conducted (see Figure 12). No difference in HER performance was observed if the suspension density was decreased to 2/3 of the initial value (see Figure 12 a and b). A further reduction of the suspension density to 1/3 of the initial value resulted in a slight decrease of the absolute hydrogen production by 11.9% (see Figure 12c and d). In contrast to these differences in the absolute hydrogen

Figure 12: Catalytic performance of heterogeneous light-driven HER at different suspension densities (1.0 g L^{-1} , 0.66 g L^{-1} and 0.33 g L^{-1} $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$) normalized to 1 g on the 3 L SLPR scale under 365 nm LED irradiation SLPR at stirring (740 rpm).

amount, it must be outlined that a decrease of the suspension density by 66.6 % resulted in 2.59-fold increase of the TON from 29 to 75 and an increase of the TOF (0.023 to 0.059 min^{-1}) by a factor of 2.58. The possibility to reduce the suspension density without major performance sacrifices depicts a significant benefit in terms of cost-efficiency for the deployment of $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ in scaled applications. Figure 12 depicts a mass normalized analysis of light-driven HER performance with decreasing suspension density. Based on the performed mass normalization, a 155.7 % increase in HER performance can be reported but it should be noted that mass normalized performance indicators should be used with care since these indicators frequently scale non-linearly^[54].

From the presented results it can be concluded that photon flux normalization enables a scale-independent comparison of homogeneous and heterogeneous MoS-based photocatalytic HER systems. The mass-transport-intensified SLPR enabled linear scale-up of the heterogeneous system from the 2 mL-scale to the 0.5 L-scale while preserving full performance and photonic efficiency. The homogeneous system showed significant process intensification at 0.5 L, but experienced a major performance drop at 3 L. In contrast, the heterogeneous $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ system maintained stable performance with fewer losses upon scale-up to 3 L, demonstrating predictable behavior and suitability for scaled photoreactor applications.

Conclusions and Outlook

Scaling the homogeneous HER to 3 L revealed that the $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system cannot be transferred directly to larger scales under otherwise comparable conditions. The observed performance loss is likely caused by changes in hydrodynamics and a changing irradiation field, eventually changing reactant/light interactions. It is concluded that mass transport plays a major role for scaling light-driven catalytic systems, since it influences the dynamics of irradiation and the local concentrations of reactants and products at catalytic sites. This is particularly relevant for the $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system since it is highly sensitive to dynamic irradiation^[48]. Therefore, a detailed investigation of SLPR hydrodynamics is required to develop strategies for tailored mass transport of catalysts and substrates into the irradiated reaction zones. The long-term stability of the catalytic performance of the **{Mo₃}**-CN_x system at the 3 L scale, combined with the developed scalable synthesis and low material costs, renders this catalytic system a highly attractive candidate for scaled photocatalytic HER. Although the performance at the 3 L scale was slightly lower than at the 0.5 L scale, optimization of the reactor design and operating conditions is expected to maintain HER performance across scales. Overall, **{Mo₃}**-CN_x represents a robust option for deployment in larger photoreactors.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals

All commercially available reagents and solvents were purchased from suppliers as follows: technical grade methanol: VWR, L-ascorbic acid: Apollo Scientific, 25 % ammonia: VWR, photosensitizer $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3](\text{PF}_6)_2$: Sigma-Aldrich, methyl orange: VWR, DMF: Thermo Scientific, melamine (99 %, Sigma-Aldrich) and methanol: (99.9%, VWR). Reagents were used directly without purification. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CN_x were synthesized following the procedure described in the sections below.

$[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ Synthesis and $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x Preparation

$[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ Synthesis

$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was synthesized according to Dave and colleagues and further used to synthesize $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ following the procedure proposed by Fedin et al.^{[55][56]}. IR characterization data of the used catalyst and can be found in the ESI (Figure 14).

$\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x Preparation (batch 1)

$\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x was prepared using a procedure proposed by Beranek et al.^[30]. SEM/EDX characterization data of the $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ loading can be found in in the ESI (section 3).

$\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ - CN_x Preparation (batch 2)

Melamine (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) and methanol (99.9%, VWR) were used as received. Heptazine-based polymeric carbon nitride (PCN) was synthesized by thermal condensation of 45 g melamine at 550 °C for 4 h in a covered crucible, using a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. After cooling to room temperature, the resulting yellow solid was washed with deionized water, dried, and finely ground using an agate mortar.

For deposition of the co-catalyst, 30 g of the as-prepared PCN were dispersed in 1800 mL methanol, covered, and sonicated for 180 min. Subsequently, 0.9 g $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, previously dissolved in 200 mL methanol, was added slowly to the dispersion under continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was stirred for more than 20 h.

After completion of the deposition process, the catalyst was recovered by filtration and centrifugation, washed three times with deionized water, and dried at 70 °C overnight. Finally, the dried material was ground to obtain the final photocatalyst.

SEM/EDX characterization data of the $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ loading can be found in in the section 3 ESI.

Photonic Characterization

Photonic characterization of the modular photoreactor and the employed light sources were performed using potassium ferrioxalate actinometry^[29,57,58] and radiometric measurements with an integrating sphere. Transmission of the 3D-printed draft-tube holder material used in the 3 L SLPR was determined by radiometric measurements using the same integrating sphere setup. A detailed description of the chemicals and experimental procedures is provided in section 5 of the ESI.

Experimental Procedure Catalysis Modular Photoreactor

All sample preparation was carried out in a glovebox under an argon atmosphere. For HER experiments, eight 5 mL GC vials were filled with 2 mL of the respective reaction mixture and equipped with PTFE-coated magnetic stirring bars (3 × 6 mm). The vials were capped with screw caps and positioned in the modular photoreactor on a magnetic stirrer, with the stirring speed set to 500-600 rpm for stirred experiments. The vials were placed in the 8-vial circular sample holder ($\varnothing = 46.4$ mm) at a vertical distance of 7 cm from the irradiation module and aligned using an additional 8-vial alignment ring at 6 cm. The modular photoreactor corpus (90 × 90 × 100 mm) was 3D-printed from white PLA (Raise3D Premium)^[29].

Irradiation was performed using LEDs with wavelengths of 365 nm and 455 nm (New Energy, LST1-01G01-UV01-00 and LST1-01F06-RYL1-00) with a fan ($26 \text{ L} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) ventilating the reaction chamber to prevent overheating. Hydrogen evolution was monitored by serial probing of the vial headspace using a calibrated gas chromatograph (Bruker Scion SQ, TCD detector), injecting 100 μL of the gas phase with argon as carrier gas. At defined intervals, irradiation was paused and a vial was randomly removed. Each removed vial was replaced by a dummy vial containing 2 mL of saturated aqueous methyl orange solution to maintain consistent photon distribution and ensure stability in the sample holder. This procedure was repeated until all vials were sampled at their designated time points.

Homogeneous Catalytic System

Sample preparation for homogeneous catalysis in the modular photoreactor followed the procedure reported by Kowalczyk et al.^[29] for a methanol/water (9:1 v/v) solvent mixture. First, a 1 M ascorbic acid (H_2A) solution was prepared and adjusted to pH 4 using 25 % ammonia solution. The required volume of ammonia was determined by stepwise addition to 8 mL of 1 M H_2A solution, measuring the pH with a Thermo Scientific Orion Star A211, and recording the amounts added until pH 4 was reached.

For further preparation, a 1.1634 M ($1 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) PS solution was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3](\text{PF}_6)_2$ in methanol. A 32.18 μM catalyst solution was prepared by dissolving the corresponding amount of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1/40 of the final

solution volume in DMF, followed by addition of 39 volumes of methanol to reach a final 32.18 μM $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ solution.

For each experiment, 8 GC vials ($V_r = 2 \text{ mL}$) were prepared. Sequentially, 18.64 μL $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ solution, 1.747 μL methanol, 34.4 μL PS solution, and 200 μL H_2A solution were pipetted into each vial. This resulted in a methanol/water ratio of 9:1 (v/v) and final concentrations of $c(\{\text{Mo}_3\}) = 0.3 \mu\text{M}$, $c([\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}) = 20 \mu\text{M}$, $c(\text{H}_2\text{A}) = 100 \text{ mM}$. Vials were then sealed, shaken, and removed from the glovebox.

Irradiation was conducted using a 455 nm LED ($I = 416 \text{ mA}$), irradiation was conducted as quickly as possible after sample preparation

Heterogeneous Catalytic System

For heterogeneous catalysis, 2 mg of $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ catalyst was weighed into each 5 mL GC vial and transferred into the glovebox. A 0.1 M H_2A solution in a methanol/water mixture (9:1 v/v) was prepared by dissolving ascorbic acid in deionized water followed by addition of the appropriate volume of methanol. Subsequently, 2 mL of this solution was added to each vial containing the catalyst, vials were capped, shaken, and removed from the glovebox. This resulted in a suspension concentration of $1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ and H_2A concentration of 0.1 M.

Irradiation was conducted using a 365 nm LED ($I = 290 \text{ mA}$), the heterogeneous vials were briefly sonicated for 1 min immediately prior to irradiation. In all cases, irradiation was conducted as quickly as possible after sample preparation and any ultrasonic treatment.

A detailed description of the used reactor setup can be found in in the ESI (Figures 1).

Experimental Procedure Catalysis and 0.5 L Loop Reactor Operation

Homogeneous

For homogeneous HER using the $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ catalyst and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ photosensitizer, 0.1 mg $\{\text{Mo}_3\}$ was dissolved in 0.110 mL DMF. After complete dissolution, 4.271 mL methanol was added and mixed, resulting in a 32.18 μM catalyst solution. The photosensitizer solution was prepared by dissolving 8.084 mg $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3](\text{PF}_6)_2$ in 8.084 mL methanol. A 1 M ascorbic acid (H_2A) solution was prepared and adjusted to pH 4 with 1.7 mL of 25 % NH_3 solution. In a graduated cylinder, 410 mL methanol was added to the reactor, followed by the photosensitizer and catalyst solutions. Then, 47 mL of the H_2A solution was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 740 rpm under a $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ flow of argon, and the reactor was cooled to 22° C . 40 min after addition of all components, irradiation was started using two sets of three 455 nm LEDs ($I = 941 \text{ mA}$). The final solution composition with a MeOH: H_2O ratio of 9:1 (v/v) was $c(\{\text{Mo}_3\}) = 0.3 \mu\text{M}$, $c([\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}) = 20 \mu\text{M}$, and $c(\text{H}_2\text{A}) = 100 \text{ mM}$.

Heterogeneous

For heterogeneous HER using the $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ catalyst, 8.454 g ascorbic acid (H_2A) was dissolved in 70 mL demineralized water. To 480 mg catalyst, 9 mL demineralized water and 1 mL methanol were added. A 500 mL graduated cylinder was filled with 47 mL methanol, then topped to ~ 250 mL with demineralized water. The H_2A solution was added and the volume was adjusted to 450 mL with demineralized water. The mixture was transferred to the reactor. The stirrer was initially set to 240 rpm, and argon flow was started and gradually increased to $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. The catalyst suspension was treated in an ultrasonic bath for 1 min and then added to the reactor. The vessel was rinsed with 20 mL demineralized water, which was also added to the reactor.

The reactor was sealed, and stirring was set to 740 rpm. The argon flow rate was maintained at $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, and the cooling temperature set to $22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. GC measurements were initiated. 40 min after addition of all components, irradiation was started using two sets of three 365 nm LEDs ($I = 770 \text{ mA}$).

3 L SLPR

For 3 L SLPR experiments, all procedures were scaled by a factor of 6. Cooling temperatures were reduced to $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to avoid overheating and excessive evaporation. After addition of all reaction components, the SLPR was inertized under constant argon flow (Argon 5.0, 99.9995 % purity, 5 bar, $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$) for 1.5 h prior to irradiation. Irradiation was performed using $72 \times 455 \text{ nm}$ LEDs ($I = 423 \text{ mA}$) and $72 \times 365 \text{ nm}$ LEDs ($I = 290 \text{ mA}$). Experiments were conducted using 8 LED modules each consisting of 9 LEDs. For experiments conducted at reduced photon flux 6 LED modules were used.

GC Measurements

Continuous hydrogen monitoring was performed using a GC (Thermo Scientific Trace 1310, TCD detector) with sampling every 11 min. Pure argon gas was fed into the reactor through a lower inlet, with flow controlled via a mass flow controller (F-201CV-200-RGD-11-E, Bronkhorst). The molar production rates of H_2 were calculated using the ideal gas law based on a set argon flowrate through the loop reactor of $75 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, controlled by the mass flow controller.

A detailed description of the used reactor setup can be found in in the ESI (Figures 2 and 3).

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